

Studies in Catalytic Dehydrogenation. Part IX. Synthesis and Dehydrogenation of Spiro-(5,5)undecanes

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Synthesis of 8,9-benzo-spiro-(5,5)undecanes with alkyl substituent in the spiran ring has been described. When these spirans are heated with Pd-C at 360-80° in a sealed tube, dehydrogenation, accompanied with ring transformation, occurs, affording a phenanthrene derivative as the main product.

Synthesis and selenium dehydrogenation of a few 8,9-benzo-spiro-(5,5)undecanes without any alkyl substituent in the spiran ring had been described earlier¹. We have now synthesised several alkylated spiro-(5,5)undecanes, i. e., spirans with two six-carbon ring systems having a common carbon atom, with a view to studying ring transformation and also the fate of the alkyl substituent present in the spiro-cyclohexane ring during their catalytic dehydrogenation. It has been noted that 1-methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(5,5)undecane (V: R₃ = R₂ = H; R₁ = Me), when heated with Pd-C at 340-50° in a metal bath, the spiro-hydrocarbon is not affected, no hydrogen is evolved, and the original hydrocarbon is fully recovered. When, however, this spiran is heated at a still higher temperature between 360° and 380° with the same catalyst in a sealed pyrex tube, dehydrogenation, accompanied with ring transformation and loss of one carbon atom, takes place, yielding 1-methylphenanthrene as the only product of dehydrogenation. Under a similar condition, 3-methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(5,5)undecane (V: R₃ = R₁ = H; R₂ = Me), 3,3'-dimethyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(5,5)undecane (V: R₃ = R₂ = Me; R₁ = H), and 1-ethyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(5,5)undecan-10-ol (IV: R₃ = R₂ = H; R₁ = Et) gave respectively 3-methylphenanthrene, 3,6-dimethylphenanthrene, and 1-ethylphenanthrene as the dehydrogenation products. In all these cases, dehydrogenation, accompanied with ring transformation, takes place with the loss of one carbon atom, furnishing ultimately a phenanthrene derivative.

It is difficult to offer a satisfactory mechanism to explain ring transformation during catalytic dehydrogenation of these spirans. We may, however, interpret the ring transformation and loss of one carbon atom of the spirans (V) by the following steps. The six-carbon ring, fused to the aromatic ring, is partially dehydrogenated at first and then the alkylated spiro-cyclohexane ring opens, away from the alkyl group along the dotted line, as shown in formula (VI), with the formation of an intermediate (VII) which then ring-closes preferentially in the angular manner, forming a phenanthrene derivative (VIII) with an angular methyl group. This intermediate loses the angular methyl group during aromatisation, providing an alkyl phenanthrene. Alternative explanations of the mechanism are possible, but the suggested one satisfactorily explains the formation of the alkyl phenanthrenes that we have isolated as dehydrogenation products.

For the synthesis of 1-methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(5,5)undecane (V: $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Me$), anhydride of 2-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid was condensed with benzene in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, affording $\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-methylcyclohexane)- β -benzoylpropionic acid (I: $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Me$). The keto-acid on the Clemmensen reduction provided $\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-methylcyclohexane)- γ -phenylbutyric acid (II: $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Me$) which was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid mixture, yielding 1-methyl-8,9-benzo-10-keto-spiro-(5,5)undecane (III: $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Me$). The spiran-ketone on the Clemmensen reduction furnished 1-methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(5,5)undecane (V: $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Me$).

In a similar manner, 3-methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro(5,5)undecane (V: $R_3 = R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Me$) has been synthesised, starting from benzene and anhydride of 4-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid. During synthesis of 3,3'-dimethyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(5,5)-undecane (V: $R_3 = R_2 = Me$; $R_1 = H$), starting from anhydride of 4-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid and toluene, it was noted that the γ -arylbutyric acid (II: $R_3 = R_2 = Me$; $R_1 = H$) could not be successfully cyclised by heating with polyphosphoric acid mixture. It was therefore converted into the corresponding acid chloride and cyclised by Friedel-Crafts' method to 3,3'-dimethyl-8,9-benzo-10-keto-spiro-(5,5)-undecane (III: $R_3 = R_2 = Me$; $R_1 = H$). During synthesis of 1-ethyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(5,5)undecane (IV: $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Et$), starting from the anhydride of 2-ethylcyclo-

hexano-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid and benzene, it was found that the keto-acid (I: $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Et$) could not be reduced satisfactorily by the Clemmensen method; the main product was a bimolecular and complex reduction-product mixture. So the keto-acid was reduced catalytically with hydrogen in presence of Pd-C to the corresponding butyric acid (II: $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Et$).

The presence of $-CO.CH_2-$ grouping in all the keto-acids (I) follows from the observation that these form a pyrylium salt with salicylaldehyde in presence of dry hydrogen chloride.

EXPERIMENTAL

The alkylated cyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acids, required for the present investigation, were prepared from alkyl cyclohexanones and ethyl cyanoacetate according to the methods of Lapworth and McRae² and Harding and Haworth³ as improved by Cope⁴. In the present investigation the separation of the stereoisomers of alkyl cyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acids was not necessary and the mixture was converted into the anhydride.

2-Methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid was prepared from 2-methylcyclohexanone and ethyl cyanoacetate. It was crystallised from HCl (dil.) in needles, m.p. 166°. (Found: C, 60.1; H, 7.9. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{16}O_4$: C, 60.0; H, 8.0%). The two stereoisomers of this acid were isolated earlier by Desai *et al.*⁵. The anhydride of the acid was obtained as a thick oil, b.p. 145-146°/5mm. (Found: C, 65.83; H, 7.5. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{14}O_3$: C, 65.93; H, 7.69%).

1-Methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-hydrocarbon

$\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-Methylcyclohexane)- β -benzoylpropionic Acid (I: $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Me$).—Powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (58 g.) was gradually added to an ice-cold solution of the anhydride of 2-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (36 g.) in dry benzene (120 ml). The mixture was kept at room temperature for 12 hours and then warmed at 60-65° for half an hour. The product was decomposed with ice and HCl and excess of benzene removed by steam distillation. The solid product was extracted with a hot sodium carbonate solution and charcoalsed; the keto-acid was precipitated with HCl and crystallised from benzene-hexane mixture. After recrystallisation from petroleum (b.p. 80-100°) it melted at 135-136°; yield 25 g. (Found: C, 73.8; H, 7.7. $C_{16}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 73.84; H, 7.69%).

Pyrylium derivative of the keto-acid (I: $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Me$) separated from the mixture of the keto-acid (0.1 g.) and salicylaldehyde (0.1 g.) in ethanol (10 ml), saturated with dry HCl, kept at 0° for 3 days. It was readily soluble in alkali and did not melt up to 290°.

$\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-Methylcyclohexane)- γ -phenylbutyric Acid (II: $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Me$).—The keto-acid (I: $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Me$) (40 g.) was reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (160 g.) and HCl (conc., 160 ml) for 18 hours. The product was extracted with

2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2754.

3. *Ibid.*, 1910, 99, 486.

4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 3453.

5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 416.

ether; the extract was washed with water and the ether distilled. The residue was extracted with a hot dilute sodium carbonate solution and acidified with HCl, when the reduced acid separated as a thick pasty mass. It was extracted with ether, dried (Na_2SO_4), and distilled as a heavy viscous mass; b.p. $190-95^\circ/1$ mm, yield 25 g. It did not solidify. (Found: C, 78.10; H, 8.81. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 78.04; H, 8.94%).

1-Methyl-8,9-benzo-10-keto-spiro-(5,5)undecane (III : $\text{R}_3 = \text{R}_4 = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{Me}$).—The above reduced acid (16 g.) was mixed with polyphosphoric acid (P_2O_5 , 96 g.; 89% H_3PO_4 , 96ml) and the mixture was heated on a steam bath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours with stirring. The product was poured on crushed ice and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with ammonia and then with water. It was dried (Na_2SO_4) and distilled as a light straw-coloured liquid; b.p. $180-85^\circ/6$ mm, yield 10 g. (Found: C, 84.1; H, 8.63. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.21; H, 8.77%).

1-Methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(5,5)undecane (V : $\text{R}_3 = \text{R}_4 = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{Me}$).—The spiro-ketone (III : $\text{R}_3 = \text{R}_4 = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{Me}$) (8 g.) was reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (32 g.) and HCl (conc., 32 ml) for 24 hours. It was extracted with ether, dried, and distilled as a colorless liquid; b.p. $145^\circ/1$ mm, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 89.8; H, 10.15. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{22}$ requires C, 89.72; H, 10.28%).

Catalytic Dehydrogenation of 1-Methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro (5,5)undecane (V: $\text{R}_3 = \text{R}_4 = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{Me}$).—The spiro-hydrocarbon (2 g.) was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.2 g.) in a sealed pyrex tube at $360-80^\circ$ for 18 hours. While opening the sealed tube, the issuing gas burnt with a blue flame. The product was extracted with ether, the solvent removed, and the residual oil subjected to chromatographic fractionation on Brockmann alumina with hexane. Eluates, each 10 ml, were collected. The first and second eluates contained only unaltered liquid spiro-hydrocarbon. The third, fourth, and fifth eluates provided colorless flakes on removal of the solvent. The solids were separately converted into picrates in hot ethanolic solution. The separated picrate after crystallisation from methanol was obtained in each case as orange needles, melting at 139° . The mixed m.p. with the picrate of an authentic sample of 1-methylphenanthrene was not depressed.

The hydrocarbon was regenerated from the picrate by eluting with hexane over Brockmann alumina and crystallised from ethanol in colorless flakes, m.p. 118° . The mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of 1-methylphenanthrene remained unaltered. (Found: C, 93.6; H, 6.3. Calc. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}$: C, 93.75; H, 6.25%).

The T. N. B. complex, prepared from the purified hydrocarbon, crystallised from ethanol in long orange needles, m.p. $160-61^\circ$. (Found: C, 62.1; H, 3.5; N, 10.24. Calc. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_6\text{N}_3$: C, 62.22; H, 3.7; N, 10.37%).

3-Methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-hydrocarbon

4-Methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid was prepared from 4-methylcyclohexanone and cyanoacetic ester. The acid obtained was a mixture of stereoisomers, m.p. $137-40^\circ$. The stereoisomeric acids were separated by Khuda⁶ and by Desai *et al.*⁷ The

mixture of stereoisomeric acids was converted into the anhydride by heating with acetic anhydride and was obtained as a thick oil, b.p. 140-42°/5 mm, which solidified on cooling.

$\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-Methylcyclohexane)- β -benzoylpropionic acid (I : $R_3 = R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Me$) was prepared from the anhydride of 4-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (36 g.), benzene (120 ml), and anhydrous aluminium chloride (58 g.) exactly as in the case of the keto-acid (I : $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Me$). It was crystallised from petroleum (b.p. 80-100°), m.p. 120-21°, yield 22 g. (Found: C, 73.92; H, 7.56. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{24}O_3$: C, 73.84; H, 7.69%). Two stereoisomers of this keto-acid were prepared by Desai *et al.*³

Pyrylium derivative of the keto-acid was prepared in the usual way. It was readily soluble in alkali and did not melt up to 290°.

$\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-Methylcyclohexane)- γ -phenylbutyric Acid (II : $R_3 = R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Me$).—The keto-acid (I : $R_3 = R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Me$) (40 g.) was reduced and the resulting product purified as in the case of the keto-acid (II : $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Me$). The residue after removal of the ether distilled as a heavy viscous mass at 250-55°/5 mm, which soon solidified. This was crystallised from petroleum (b.p. 80-100°), m.p. 115-16°, yield 30 g. (Found : C, 78.12; H, 8.83. $C_{16}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 78.04; H, 8.94%).

3-Methyl-8,9-benzo-10-keto-spiro-(5,5)undecane (III : $R_3 = R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Me$).—The butyric acid (II : $R_3 = R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Me$) (15 g.) was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid (P_2O_5 , 90 g. and 89% H_3PO_4 , 90 ml) as in the preparation of the spiro-ketone (III: $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Me$). It is a light straw-coloured liquid, b.p. 175-77°/5 mm, yield 9 g. (Found: C, 84.3; H, 8.68. $C_{16}H_{20}O$ requires C, 84.21; H, 8.77%).

3-Methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(5,5)undecane (V : $R_3 = R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Me$).—The spiro-ketone (III : $R_3 = R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Me$) (6 g.) was reduced with amalgamated zinc (24 g.) and HCl (conc., 24 ml) for 24 hours. It is a colorless oil, b.p. 160°/5 mm, yield 4 g. (Found: C, 89.83; H, 10.20. $C_{16}H_{22}$ requires C, 89.72; H, 10.28%).

Catalytic Dehydrogenation of the Spiro-hydrocarbon (V : $R_3 = R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Me$).—The spiro-hydrocarbon (3 g.) was reduced with Pd-C catalyst and subjected to chromatographic fractionation in the same way as in the case of the 1-methyl isomer (V : $R_1 = Me$). The first and the second eluates contained only unaltered spiro-hydrocarbon. The third, fourth, and fifth eluates left oily residues after removal of the solvent. T.N.B. complex, prepared separately, melted at 153-54°. (Found: C, 62.1; H, 3.9; N, 10.4. $C_{21}H_{15}O_6N_3$ requires C, 62.22; H, 3.70; N, 10.37%).

The hydrocarbon was regenerated from the T. N. B. complex by eluting with hexane over Brockmann alumina and crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 62-63°. The mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of 3-methylphenanthrene remained unaltered. (Found: C, 93.6; H, 6.3. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{16}$: C, 93.75; H, 6.25%).

The trinitrofluorenone derivative was prepared from the purified hydrocarbon and crystallised from ethanol in long orange needles, m.p. 168-69°. (Found: C, 66.13; H, 3.4; N, 8.3. $C_{23}H_{17}O_7N_3$ requires C, 66.27; H, 3.35; N, 8.28%).

3,3'-Dimethyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-hydrocarbon

$\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-Methylcyclohexane)- β -(p-toluy)propionic Acid (I : $R_3 = R_2 = Me$; $R_1 = H$) was prepared from the anhydride of 4-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (72 g.),

toluene (200 ml), and anhydrous aluminium chloride (116 g.) exactly as in the case of the keto-acid (I : $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Me$). It was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 165-66°, yield 50 g. (Found: C, 74.35; H, 8.1. $C_{17}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 74.45; H, 8.03%).

Pyrylium derivative of the keto-acid (I : $R_3 = R_2 = Me$; $R_1 = H$) separated from the mixture of the keto-acid (0.1 g.) and salicylaldehyde (0.1 g.) in ethanol (10 ml), saturated with dry HCl gas, kept at 0° for 3 days. It was readily soluble in alkali and did not melt up to 290°.

$\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-Methylcyclohexane)- γ -(p-tolyl)butyric Acid (II : $R_3 = R_2 = Me$; $R_1 = H$).—The keto-acid (I : $R_3 = R_2 = Me$; $R_1 = H$) (30 g.) was reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (120 g.) and HCl (conc., 120 ml) for 24 hours. The product was purified as in the case of the keto-acid (II : $R_3 = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = Me$). The residue after removal of the ether was crystallised from petroleum (b.p. 60-80°), m.p. 155-56°, yield 20 g. (Found: C, 78.34; H, 9.3. $C_{17}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 78.46; H, 9.23%).

3,3'-Dimethyl-8,9-benzo-10-keto-spiro-(5,5) underane (III : $R_3 = R_2 = Me$; $R_1 = H$).—The reduced acid (II : $R_3 = R_2 = Me$; $R_1 = H$) (26 g.) was converted into the corresponding acid chloride by heating with thionyl chloride on a steam bath for half an hour. The acid chloride was dissolved in dry petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (15 g.) was added. The spiro-ketone distilled as a light straw-coloured oil with a characteristic odour, b.p. 160-62°/5 mm, yield 12 g. (Found: C, 84.22; H, 10.0. $C_{17}H_{22}O$ requires C, 84.29; H, 9.09%).

3,3'-Dimethyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(5,5)undecane (V : $R_3 = R_2 = Me$; $R_1 = H$).—The spiro-ketone (III : $R_3 = R_2 = Me$; $R_1 = H$) (10 g.) was reduced with amalgamated zinc (40 g.) and HCl (conc., 40 ml) by heating for 24 hours. It is a colorless liquid, b.p. 150-52°/1mm, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 89.32; H, 10.60. $C_{17}H_{24}$ requires C, 89.47; H, 10.52%).

Catalytic Dehydrogenation of the Spiro-hydrocarbon (V : $R_3 = R_2 = Me$; $R_1 = H$).—The spiro-hydrocarbon (3 g.) was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.3 g.) in a sealed pyrex tube at 360-80° for 18 hours. The product was subjected to chromatographic fractionation as in previous cases. The first and second eluates contained only unaltered spiro-hydrocarbon. The third, fourth, and fifth eluates provided colorless solids on removal of the solvent. T.N.B. complex, prepared separately, after recrystallisation from methanol was obtained in each case as orange needles, m.p. 146-47°. (Found, C, 62.9; H, 4.1; N, 13.1. $C_{22}H_{17}O_6N_3$ requires C, 63.00; H, 4.05; N, 10.02%).

The hydrocarbon was regenerated from the T. N. B. complex and crystallised from ethanol in colorless flakes, m.p. 141-42°. (Found: C, 93.31; H, 6.7. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}$: C, 93.20; H, 6.79%).

The picrate, prepared from the purified hydrocarbon, was crystallised from methanol in orange needles, m.p. 172-73°. (Found: C, 60.72; H, 3.8; N, 9.7. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{17}O_7N_3$: C, 60.68; H, 3.90; N, 9.65%).

Haworth⁷ recorded the m.p. of 3,6-dimethylphenanthrone as 141° and that of its picrate as 172-73°.

1- *Ethyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-hydrocarbon*

Ethyl 2-ethylcyclohexylidenecyanoacetate was prepared, starting from 2-ethylcyclohexanone (138 g.), ethyl cyanoacetate (113 g.), ammonium acetate (8 g.), acetic acid (12 ml), and benzene (160 ml) according to the method of Cope⁴. The condensation product was collected at 145-50°/6 mm as a colorless oil, yield 210 g. (Found: C, 70.58; H, 8.69; N, 6.35. $C_{15}H_{19}O_2N$ requires C, 70.58; H, 8.59; N, 6.33%).

2-Ethylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid was prepared by addition of KCN (117 g.) to ethyl 2-ethylcyclohexylidenecyanoacetate (198 g.) and subsequent hydrolysis with a mixture of HCl (conc., 900 ml) and glacial acetic acid (300 ml) by heating for 36 hours. It was crystallised from HCl (dil.) in stout cubes and then from petroleum (60-80°), m.p. 158-59°, yield 140 g. (Found: C, 61.53; H, 8.5. $C_{11}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 61.68; H, 8.41%).

The *anhydride* of the acid was obtained as a thick oil, b.p. 164-65°/7 mm. (Found: C, 67.22; H, 8.2. $C_{11}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 67.34; H, 8.16%).

$\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-*Ethylcyclohexane*)- β -*benzoylpropionic Acid* (I: $R_3=R_2=H$; $R_1=Et$) was prepared, starting from the anhydride of 2-ethylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (39 g.), dry benzene (120 ml), and aluminium chloride (58 g.), exactly as in the case of the keto-acid (I: $R_3=R_2=H$; $R_1=Me$). It was obtained as a heavy, viscous, colorless mass with a green fluorescence; b.p. 185-87°/1 mm., yield 25 g. (Found: C, 74.32; H, 8.1. $C_{17}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 74.45; H, 8.03%).

Pyrylium derivative of the keto-acid was prepared in the usual way. It was readily soluble in alkali and did not melt up to 290°.

$\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-*Ethylcyclohexane*)- γ -*phenylbutyric Acid* (II: $R_3=R_2=H$; $R_1=Et$).—The keto-acid (I: $R_3=R_2=H$; $R_1=Et$) (12 g.) was subjected to catalytic hydrogenation in presence of Pd-C (1.2 g., 10%) in ethanolic solution under 10 atmospheres at 55-60°. The required amount of hydrogen was absorbed in an hour. It was obtained as a thick colorless liquid; b.p. 175-80°/0.2 mm, yield 10.5 g. (Found: C, 78.5; H, 9.12. $C_{17}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 78.46; H, 9.23%).

1-*Ethyl-8,9-benzo-10-keto-spiro-(5,5)undecane* (III: $R_3=R_2=H$; $R_1=Et$).—The reduced acid (II: $R_3=R_2=H$; $R_1=Et$) (8 g.) was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid as in the former cases. The spiro-ketone distilled at 164-66°/3 mm as a light straw-coloured liquid, with a characteristic odour; yield 5 g. (Found: C, 84.1; H, 10.0. $C_{17}H_{24}O$ requires C, 84.29; H, 9.09%).

1-*Ethyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(5,5)undecan-10-ol* (IV: $R_3=R_2=H$; $R_1=Et$).—The spiro-ketone (III: $R_3=R_2=H$; $R_1=Et$) (4 g.) in dry ether (30 ml) was gradually added to a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (4 g.) in dry ether (100 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hours and worked up as usual. The distillate was collected at 170-71°/2 mm as a thick colorless liquid; yield 3 g. (Found: C, 83.5; H, 9.9. $C_{17}H_{24}O$ requires C, 83.60; H, 9.83%).

Catalytic Dehydrogenation of 1-Ethyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(5,5)undecan-10-ol (IV: $R_3=R_2=H$; $R_1=Et$).—The spiro-compound (2.5 g.) was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.3 g.) in a sealed pyrex tube at 360-80° for 20 hours. The product was subjected to chromatographic fractionation on Brockmann alumina with hexane. The first and second

eluates contained only unchanged spiro-hydrocarbon. The third, fourth, and fifth eluates provided colorless flakes with greenish blue fluorescence on removal of the solvent. The solids were separately converted into trinitrobenzene complex in ethanol. The complex was repeatedly crystallised from ethanol and finally recrystallised from methanol. In every case T.N.B. complex was obtained as orange needles, m.p. 164-65°. (Found: C, 63.10; H, 3.90; N, 10.10. $C_{22}H_{17}O_6N_3$ requires C, 63.00; H, 4.05; N, 10.02%).

The regenerated hydrocarbon crystallised from methanol in shining flakes with fluorescence, m.p. 62-63°. (Found: C, 93.1; H, 6.8. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}$: C, 93.20; H, 6.79%).

The picrate, prepared from the purified hydrocarbon, crystallised from methanol in slender orange prisms, m.p. 108-109°. (Found: C, 60.55; H, 3.8; N, 9.75. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{17}O_7N_3$: C, 60.68; H, 3.90; N, 9.65%).

Haworth⁷ recorded the m.p. of 1-ethylphenanthrene as 62.5° and that of its picrate as 108-109°.

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